

A NEW METHOD OF PREPARING HYDROSOLS OF SHELLAC AND OTHER NATURAL RESINS AND THEIR PROPERTIES.

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A method for the preparation of concentrated clear hydrosols of shellac, rosin, mastic, etc. has been described, and a brief study of their physico-chemical and colloidal properties has been made. The shellac sols have been found to produce thin, transparent varnish films on air-drying which are more hard and water-resistant than ordinary shellac films from French polish.

Hydrosols of resins like mastic, gamboge, shellac, etc. have been prepared and studied by a number of workers. These sols are generally prepared by the method, perhaps first used by Spring (*vide* Burton, "Physical Properties of Colloidal Solutions", p. 18), of pouring a small quantity of alcoholic or ethereal solution of the resin in cold or boiling water and the subsequent expulsion of the organic solvent by heating. This method has the drawback that the sols are, as a rule, milky-opaque having a preponderance of coarse microscopic particles and contain a very small quantity of the dispersed phase (about 0.1 g. per litre). The present paper deals with a different method of producing transparent concentrated hydrosols of the resins and a study of their properties.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Method of Preparation.

The method, in short, consists in dialysing an ammoniacal solution of the resin when free ammonia diffuses out and the ammonium salt of the resin suffers membrane hydrolysis leading to the formation of a colloidal solution of the resin.

The resins (about 5-15 g.) were dissolved in 100 c.c. of ammonium hydroxide (0.1-0.5N) to a slight excess of ammonia. After filtration the solution was dialysed in thin cellophane (P. T. 300) or collodion bags against distilled water which was changed twice a day. With the progress of dialysis colloidal properties began to appear as evidenced by the ease of coagulation of the resin by the addition of $N/2$ -potassium chloride to a small portion of the solution. Dialysis was continued until the dialysate

gave a slight colouration (no precipitate) with Nessler's solution and only a faint opalescence on addition of dilute hydrochloric acid or alum solution. This was achieved in about four or five days with the thin cellophane membranes (P.T. 300), and in two to three days with the collodion membranes. The criteria of formation of a good sol are that it should be transparent, neutral or very faintly acidic, and easily coagulable by the addition of about its own volume of 0.5*N*-potassium chloride solution. If dialysis is continued for a much longer time, the sol gradually turns opalescent and becomes increasingly sensitive to electrolytes. Such over-dialysed sols either tend to form soft gel-like mass or separate coarse precipitates on keeping.

A method of further purification of the sol thus obtained, which has been found to be very suitable for the rosin sol, is to ultrafilter the sol and to treat the still moist residue on the ultrafilter with water when the residue disperses to form a faintly acidic (p_H 5 to 5.5), stable and transparent sol which shows no tendency to settle or separate any coagulum even on keeping for over six months. Other alkalis like sodium carbonate or borax have also been used with success but the yield is somewhat less in these cases.

The properties of the final sol are found to depend on the initial concentrations of ammonia and the resin, and also on the rate and extent of dialysis. The sols contain ammonia to the extent of about 10 to 45% of the total equivalent of the resin acid present in the sol. This small concentration of ammonia is necessary for the stability of the sol and removed by prolonging the dialysis, the sol coarsens and ultimately coagulates on keeping. This method has been applied with success in the cases of shellac, bleached shellac, rosin, abietic acid and mastic.

Physical and Chemical Properties.

The sols thus produced are clear, transparent liquids usually having p_H values between 6.6 and 7.2 for shellac sols and between 5.0 and 5.5 for rosin sols. Due to considerable osmosis and the diffusion of the resin anions during dialysis the concentration of the final sol is much less than that originally taken, but the sols can be concentrated to any desired concentration by slowly evaporating on the water-bath, if the concentration of ammonia in the sol is not below a certain critical amount. The properties of some typical sols prepared by this method are summarised in the following table.

TABLE I.

	Shellac hydrosol.		Rosin sol:
	I	II	
1. Appearance	Transparent.	Transparent, slightly hazy in reflected light	Clear in transmitted light, opalescent in reflected light
2. Conc. of resin (g. per 100 g. of water)	3.72	3.2	0.79
3. Conc. of ammonia in the sol in normality	0.025	0.017	0.0031
4. Sp. conductivity (mhos) at 30°	1.38×10^{-3}	1.33×10^{-3}	1.48×10^{-4}
5. p_H	7.23	7.10	5.42
6. Relative density (30°)	1.0058	1.0056	1.0010
7. Relative viscosity (30°)	1.30	1.24	1.04

The concentration of the resin was determined by evaporating to dryness a known weight of the sol and then heating for about 2-3 hours at 90-95° until the weight remained fairly constant. Ammonia was estimated by micro-Kjeldahl method according to the directions of Pregl "Organic Microanalysis", p_H values were determined with a glass electrode (Morton's type) assembled with a Cambridge valve potentiometer. All other constants in the above table were determined by the usual apparatus.

A simple calculation from the known acid values of the resins (Shellac, 70; Rosin, 160) shows that the stabilising electrolyte (ammonia) is present in such concentrations as to neutralise only 10-50% of the total resin acid present. In fact, the shellac sols prepared by this method are not very stable on keeping if the concentration of ammonia is not sufficient to neutralise at least 25% of the total acidity of the resin, but with rosin sols, except for a slight haziness, there is hardly any loss of stability even with concentrations of ammonia capable of neutralising only 10% of the total acidity of the rosin.

Colloidal Properties.

The sols show strong Tyndall effect, which is easily visible with illumination from a powerful source of light in a dark room.

The sols do not pass through ultrafilters as proved by analyses of their ultrafiltrates. The results are shown in Table II. A Zsigmondy type 9 cm. ultrafilter bed with commercial ultrafilters manufactured by de Haen & Co. were used. The sols were first ultrafiltered through 'membranefilters' (fine) and then through 'ultrafilter' (fine), the latter being capable of retaining very fine colloids like gold sol, albumen, etc.

TABLE II.

	Shellac sol I.		Shellac sol II.		Rosin sol.	
	Original.	Ultrafiltrate.	Original.	Ultrafiltrate.	Original.	Ultrafiltrate.
1. Residue on evaporation of 10 c.c.	0.361	0.014	0.262	0.0134	0.0786	0.004
2. Concentration of ammonia	—	—	0.0124	0.0012	0.0031	trace

Table II shows that greater part of the ammonia in the sol is present as stabilising ions in the double layer or deeply embedded in the core of the micelles and not in the inter-micellary liquid and so does not pass into the ultrafiltrate. It will be observed that for the shellac sols about 4% of the resin pass into the ultrafiltrate, which is perhaps partly due to the extremely fine state of subdivision of the dispersed phase and partly to the presence of free ammonium salt of the resin.

The sols are coagulated by electrolytes, acids being extremely active but otherwise the coagulation follows the valency rule. Bases like caustic soda first precipitate the sol and then slowly dissolve the resin thus precipitated. In Table III are given the coagulation values with some typical electrolytes. These coagulation values or liminal concentrations were determined according to the procedure followed by Freundlich (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1903, **44**, 129) by noting the minimum concentration of the electrolytes necessary to produce visible coagulum or loss of transparency after two hours on mixing equal volumes of the sol and the electrolyte solution. To obviate the difficulty of observing coagulation due to gel formation, all coagulation experiments were carried out with sols diluted to attain a concentration of 1% solid content for shellac and 0.1% for rosin. Aluminium chloride sometimes seemed to produce 'anomalous series' effect with shellac sols.

TABLE III.

Electrolytes.	Liminal concentration (millimols/litre).		
	Shellac sol I.	Shellac sol II.	Rosin sol.
Hydrochloric acid	1.1	0.74	1.16
Potassium chloride	240.0	190.0	250.0
Barium chloride	3.8	3.2	9.0
Aluminium chloride	1.05	0.65	0.062

The coagulation values depend on the concentration of ammonia present in the sol as shown by the values (Table IV) for different samples of the same shellac sol (A_1 , A_2 , A_3 and A_4) taken out after different degrees of dialysis. The sols A_1 , A_2 , and A_3 were transparent, while sol A_4 was slightly opalescent. The rosin sol A_2 was prepared by ultrafiltering sol A_1 and then dispersing the moist residue on the ultrafilter by addition of water when it formed a stable, transparent, non-settling hydrosol. Coagulation values were determined after dilution of the sols to 1 g. of solid content per litre. It is of interest to note from a comparison of the coagulation values of the rosin sols A_1 and A_2 that the presence of a small quantity (about 5% of the total) of ammonia in the intermicellary liquid may produce a large difference in the coagulation values.

TABLE IV.

Sol.	No. of days dialysed	Conc. of resin g./1000 g. water.	Conc. of ammonia $\times 10^3$.	Coagulation value with KCl.
A_1 Shellac sol	4	1.0	0.801	355
A_2 " "	5	1.0	0.727	315
A_3 " "	7	1.0	0.586	215
A_4 " "	10	1.0	0.474	165
A_1 Rosin "	—	1.0	0.391	240
A_2 " "	—	1.0	0.372	175

Film-forming Properties.

The shellac sols have the useful property of drying to a thin transparent film at room temperature in about one or two hours. Test panels on glass

show such films to have high scratch-hardness and water resistance. These films neither show any tendency to dissolve nor bluish when kept immersed in water for 24 hours, whereas films from the ordinary spirit-shellac varnish bluish in about an hour. The films are harder consistent with the fact that the shellac in the sol contains more hard resin than ordinary shellac due to a more rapid diffusing of the soft resin during dialysis. In fact, the percentage of soft resin in the sol is found to vary between 8 and 12 as against 28% in the original shellac. It is suggested that ammoniacal solutions of shellac should be dialysed before application as varnish if it is desired to confer to them water-resisting properties, paler colour and high scratch-hardness.

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